

ESFR-SMART core burnup calculation on radially infinite lattice with Monte-Carlo code

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Purpose of the European Sodium Fast Reactor Safety Measures Assessment and Research Tools (ESFR – SMART) program is investigation of ESFR safety parameters like sodium void coefficient, and Doppler coefficient. To investigate these safety parameters over more cycles, one must use a detailed axial burnup profile of the fuel. The objective of this work is to develop a procedure which will be used for calculating the safety parameters over several cycles. Burnup calculations can be performed with both deterministic and Monte Carlo codes. However, deterministic codes have less accurate cross section statistics compared to Monte Carlo codes, whereas Monte Carlo codes require extensive computing power. To circumvent the undesired traits of Monte Carlo and deterministic codes, radially infinite core was modeled in Serpent 2. Building block of the infinite lattice consists of six fuel assemblies (batches) at different burnup stages that are representative of the core inner region. Batch burnup procedure (BBP) was adopted and developed to prepare input files for Serpent 2 burnup simulations over 6 cycles. Data of axial burnup profiles in space and time are presented and it was concluded that the BBP is suitable for investigation of safety parameters like sodium void coefficient.

KEYWORDS: *ESFR-SMART, axial burnup, multi-batch operation*

Introduction

Due to the worldwide increasing energy consumption, significant developments across the energy production sector in terms of increased efficiency, minimized environmental impact, and increased economics are yet to be achieved. Nuclear industry is not an exception as it provides 10% of worldwide electricity production and it is faced with the following, nuclear related challenges:

- Minor actinides burning
- Lowering likelihood of reactor core meltdown
- Making technology unattractive for weapons proliferation
- Lowering the financial risk

To address these challenges, six different concepts of Generation IV fission reactors were developed. One of the concepts is the sodium cooled fast reactor (SFR). In 1990s a European wide effort was made to design a concept for a commercial SFR. The reactor was named European Sodium Fast Reactor (ESFR). To better understand safety challenges of the new design a project named European Sodium Fast Reactor Safety Measures Assessment and Research Tools (ESFR-SMART) was launched in 2017 [1]. Among many safety parameters, Sodium void effect feedback and Doppler effect feedback are being investigated in the ESFR-SMART project. One approach of investigating the aforementioned parameters is burnup tracking over depletion cycles.

This paper presents a procedure for cyclic burnup calculations using Monte Carlo code Serpent 2 on a reduced ESFR-SMART geometry which enables a better understanding of axial burnup distribution in the core. Burnup calculations are usually performed with deterministic codes [2], like ERANOS, as well as Monte Carlo (MC) codes [4], like Serpent. However, deterministic codes, compared to MC codes, produce less accurate cross sections. A full core model requires complex energy and space self-shielding treatment for multigroup cross section data calculation. Thus, deterministic codes yield lower cross section statistics. To circumvent the issue of multigroup cross section data, MC codes have been extensively used for burnup calculations. MC codes use continuous energy cross sections which do not require self-shielding treatment, making MC cross sections more accurate. MC codes are usually not used for detailed burnup calculations on the whole core scale, because the required nodalization results in higher statistical error. This can be avoided; however, it effectively increases computational requirements rendering the approach impractical due to time required for execution of a simulation, which can take weeks. Therefore, another simplified approach was taken in this work.

ESFR-SMART core was simulated as radially infinite lattice of a repetitive building block representing the inner fuel region of the ESFR-SMART core. Repetitive block consists of 6 zones, referred to as batches, and it is based on ESFR-SMART 6 cycle refueling scheme; hence, the 6-batch refueling scheme was represented. To be more specific, the term “batch” refers to zones in which the fuel assemblies are at the same burnup level. Each batch contains one fuel assembly, which is divided into 20 axial nodes. Burnup calculation was performed for 12 consecutive cycles starting with core fully loaded with fresh fuel. Term “cycle” refers to irradiation time of the core, which is 350 days for the ESFR-SMART core. After each cycle, a designated fuel assembly in the base block was replaced with a fresh fuel assembly. The developed procedure can be used for estimating safety coefficients like sodium void effect over the loading cycles of fuel assemblies. Important to add is that sodium and Doppler reactivity coefficient distributions are flat in the center of the ESFR-SMART core [3]. This implicated that radially infinite lattice model is representable of the ESFR-SMART inner core.

To perform a 12-cycle simulation in Serpent 2, a Python script was derived from ScRB routine [4] and further developed to handle Serpent 2 input files, run the simulations, and to organize / analyze simulation results. The procedure is called the Batch Burnup Procedure (BBP) and unlike ScRB Ruby script, it is written in and adjusted for Python programming language. BBP was used for investigating axial burnup profiles, but it can be also used in the future for calculating safety relevant coefficients, like the sodium void coefficient, over number of cycles. Sodium void coefficient has been specifically recognized as a parameter requiring extensive investigation. A paper from Rineski et al [5] suggests using a Monte Carlo code for validating sodium void coefficients calculated by the deterministic codes [3]. BBP has a potential to do that. The objective of this work is to assess the feasibility of using the infinite lattice and BBP for calculating sodium void coefficient at different depletion stages. Power and depletion of relevant nuclides are compared with the literature and a final judgement will be made based on the discrepancies between literature and this work’s results.

ESFR-SMART Technical Specifications

ESFR-SMART [6] is designed to have an electricity output of 1500 GW and a thermal output of 3600 GW. Fuel is enriched to 17.99 %wt and it has a burnup target of 100 GWd/tHM. ESFR-SMART core (Figure 1) is divided into inner and outer region. Inner region has 216 fuel assemblies, and outer region has 288 fuel assemblies. Difference between the inner and the outer fuel assemblies is in the fissile/fertile fuel height ratio. Inner fuel assemblies have a 75:25 ratio, whereas outer fuel assemblies have a 95:5 ratio. A typical fuel assembly is depleted for 2170 days.

Each fuel assembly has an outer hexagonal wrapper (at 470° C), made of EM10 steel, with a pitch of ca. 21 cm. Each fuel assembly holds 271 fuel rods cladded by ODS Incoloy (at 470° C). Fissile fuel pellets have a central hole to reduce the radial power peak across the pellet, enabling fuel to reach higher operational temperature across the whole pellet. Fissile fuel pellets (at 1227° C) are made of mixed oxide (MOX) fuel with central hole diameter of 0.16 cm and outer diameter of 0.47cm. Fertile fuel pellets (at 627° C) have no central holes because they do not produce as much power as fissile fuel pellets. They have an outer diameter of 0.47 cm and are made of MOX material [6].

Figure 1: Core layout [7]

Serpent 2 Core design

A full ESFR-SMART core depletion simulation with Serpent 2 is challenging in terms of required computer resources. Therefore, a much simpler model, representative of the core, needs to be developed. The idea is to take a part of the ESFR-SMART core and use it as a building block for the infinite core lattice. This core model enables investigation of fine axial burnup profiles without requiring significant computational power by preserving the 6-batch reloading scheme.

Most representative part of the core is a symmetric region that contains six fuel assemblies at six different burnup levels corresponding to 6 cycle refueling regime. Symmetry is needed for construction of an infinite core lattice, where selected core region would serve as a building block. Only inner core region is considered in this work.

Figure 2 represents the process of choosing the right configuration of fuel assemblies for modeling the building block of infinite core lattice model. An inner core region is looked at for a symmetric configuration of 11 fuel assemblies. As there is no such region in the ESFR-SMART core, a configuration, which only needs minor modifications to achieve symmetry, is identified. Refer to the area marked with a rectangle in ESFR-SMART reloading scheme – Figure 2. Using that configuration as a reference, a Serpent 2 model is created. It uses the given fuel assembly configuration to create an infinite core as depicted in the bottom picture in Figure 2.

Figure 2: from ESFR-SMART core to infinite core (ESFR-SMART reloading scheme move the rectangle up left one FA, yellow should be in all corners)

For easier spatial referencing inside the base block, fuel assemblies at different depletion stages are referred to as batches and are assigned with a number from 1 to 6. In Figure 2 batch #1 is marked with color red, batch #2 is marked with color light pink, batch #3 is marked with color yellow, batch #4 is marked with color green, batch #5 is marked with color blue, and batch #6 is marked with color purple. In the initial core, all batches start with fresh fuel assemblies. Fuel assembly in batch #1 will be replaced after it spends 1 full cycle in the core, fuel assembly in batch #2 will be replaced after it spends 2 full cycles in the core, the pattern continues for batches 3, 4, 5, and 6. All fuel assemblies will be replaced with fresh ones after 7 cycles. Before starting cycle #8 a fuel assembly in batch #1 is replaced with fresh fuel. The pattern for upcoming cycles is the same as for the cycles #2 through #7.

A MC full core model is usually modeled by assigning one material card for all fuel rods or several material cards for different fuel regions, e.g. fissile vs fertile. Serpent 2 gives an option of space-wise burnup tracking and automatic nodalization of the region of interest. However, nodalizing the region of interest by manually assigning a new material card for each node yields more information about the depleted node.

Total active zone height is equal to 100.544 cm which includes fissile as well as fertile region. Active zone was axially divided into 20 nodes, 15 nodes for fissile region and 5 nodes for fertile region. This sums up to 120 material cards as there are 6 batches in the base block. Nodalization of batch #5, and a table with nodes' heights is shown in Figure 3. In addition, all components in axial direction, like the steel blanked and the plenum, are modeled by dimensions found in *Specification of the new core safety measures* [6].

Figure 3: Nodalization table with height (left), z-y plot of batch #5 (right)

Batch Burnup Procedure

Serpent 2 cannot perform a burnup calculation of one cycle, reload the core, and run a burnup calculation for a second cycle. Therefore, the process of preparing Serpent 2 input files must be automated. This was done using the BBP Python script.

Serpent 2 input files, which are the same for all burnup runs, are manually written first. These include surface input file, pins input file, etc. These files are copy – pasted from the main folder to the folder of the current simulation cycle by the script. Second, two Serpent 2 template files are also written manually. One is written for the main input file, and the other is written for the material definition card. Main input file contains paths to other Serpent 2 files like surface file, or a pin file. It also contains paths to cross section libraries as well as a neutron statistics card, a burnup card, and a volume card. Python script copy-pastes the template files into the folder of the current simulation cycle and changes paths in the main input file so that Serpent 2 input files are called from appropriate folders. Material definition card contains material cards for all 120 fuel materials in the active zone. For each cycle, python script modifies the template to account for burned fuel and reloading. Reloading outage period between cycles is accounted for in the python script. Nuclear vectors, that have not been replaced by a fresh nuclear vector, are adjusted for a 30-day decay period, which was assumed to be the average revision period for the ESRF-SMART core [8]. Once the simulation is done for 12 cycles, a separate python script collects data from all Serpent 2 output files.

Figure 4: BBP

The BBP script is based on the Semi-Continuous Refueling Burnup (ScRB) routine [4]. The ScRB routine is tuned for simulation of burnup of fuel pebbles in Pebble Bed – High Temperature Reactor (PB-HTR) and is adjusted for a programming language called Ruby. The new method, presented in this paper has following upgrades in comparison to ScRB: it is adjusted for batch loading instead of pebble loading, it is adjusted for Python programming language, and it is optimized for efficiency due to increased number of material cards. An upgraded version of ScRB is thus called Batch Burnup Procedure (BBP). Refer to Figure 4 for the BBP flowchart.

Serpent2 simulation parameters

Burnup calculations were performed by using three burnup steps: 0, 175, and 350 days. The three burnup steps represent different levels of core depletion: beginning of cycle (BOC), middle of cycle (MOC) and end of cycle (EOC). The predictor – corrector method was used for the burnup calculations. Thermal power of the reactor is 3600 MW, and it was modified for the infinite lattice core model:

$$P = 3600e06 \frac{6}{504} = 42.86e06 [W] \quad (1)$$

Total power is first divided by total number of fuel assemblies to yield power per fuel assembly. This is then multiplied by six, which is the number of fuel assemblies in the building block of an infinite lattice. The neutron source was set to 10,000 neutrons, 100 active cycles, and 20 inactive cycles. Average k_{eff} uncertainties were between 20 - 30 pcm. Libraries endfb71.xsdir, endfb71.dec, and endfb71.nfy were used in this work. Furthermore, only actinides were accounted for in the burnup calculations.

Results

Error bars were not used in this work's plots. The reason behind this is reasonably small relative errors in most of the plots. Thus, if plotted, error bars would look like a one horizontal line and would decrease the readability of the figures. To account missing error bars, the average relative errors are reported where appropriate.

Figure 5: Batch-wise power distribution of the infinite core

As the core is simulated as radially infinite lattice, neutron flux and so the power distribution should be the same for all batches at the very beginning of the first cycle. Large variance observed in Figure 5 can be caused by several factors: low number of neutrons simulated, and low number of active, and inactive cycles. To investigate for the impact of neutron statistics on the power values, cycle #1 was repeated by increasing the number of simulated neutrons from 10,000 to 100. Standard deviation of power distribution at the beginning of cycle for 100,000 neutrons was 0.006 MW and for 10,000 was 0.06 MW. This indicates that the large variance is due to low neutron statistics. A Simulation with 100,000 neutrons was not done for all 12 cycles, because a simulation for only one cycle with 100,000 neutrons took 12 hours to finish.

Note that power is held constant throughout the simulation. If power in one fuel assembly is increased by an instability caused by low statistics, power of another fuel assembly must be decreased to maintain

the given power. This makes the core inherently unstable which is exemplified by power variance through cycle 1. In addition, an average relative error of 0.4% for power of each fuel assembly at BOC (cycle 1) doesn't affect validity of the data obtained in this work.

A 12-cycle axial power profile of Batch #1 is depicted in Figure 6. One can observe many distinctive features. Magnitude of the peak as well as the total power produced by a fuel assembly is decreasing with time spent inside the core. This is namely due to production of fission products, and depletion of fissile material. The average relative error of power for all cycles is 0.009 %.

Figure 6: Axial power profile of two fuel assemblies in Batch #1, first fuel assembly is tracked from cycle #1 to #6, it is then replaced by a second fuel assembly which is tracked from cycle #7 to cycle #12

Another feature found in Figure 6 plot is a distinctive power increase at node #20 for all cycles. One would expect to see a continuously decreasing power curve at the top of the core due to axial leakage of neutrons. This feature occurs due to helium gas located in the upper gas plenum. Helium has a much smaller atomic number than sodium. Thus, it slows down neutrons more efficiently. In addition, fission cross sections for U-235 and Pu-239 are inversely proportional to neutron energy. Thus, more fission events are expected to occur for nuclear reactions with less energetic neutrons. The explanation for the distinctive power increase at the top of the core is further supported by Figure 7. Pu-239, and U-235 are depleted more at node #20 than at node #19. Furthermore, U-235 is depleted faster than Pu-239, supporting the fact that the distinctive power feature is due to neutron thermalization.

Power in Figure 6 is normalized for linear power of 268.3 W/cm. The linear power peaks at BOC for cycles #1 and #6 were compared with the literature [5, 9]. Refer to table 2 for the comparison. Note that the percentage differences between the power peaks represent a general trend in the discrepancy between the axial power profiles. For an example, each point in axial power distribution for BOC cycle #1 will on average be 7% higher than in the literature. Smaller difference of 3% for BOC in cycle #6 is function of the fuel assembly position in the core and the reloading patten of the neighboring fuel assemblies. Comparison of axial power profiles indicates that the discrepancy is satisfactory. However, in future simulations power should be adjusted to match the ESFR-SMART inner core power.

Table 1: peak linear power comparison with the literature

	BOC #1 (W/cm)	BOC #6 (W/cm)
Infinite lattice	410	370
Literature (ref. zone 37-30)	380	360
% difference	7	3

Figure 7 (left) shows axial distribution of Pu-239 in a fuel assembly placed in zone batch #1 for the first six cycles. Pu-239 atom density increases in the fertile region for all six cycles. In the fissile region, it first increases for all nodes, but after three cycle it starts to decrease. Faster depletion of Pu-239 atom density was observed for the middle of the fissile zone for cycles #3 through #6, whereas the top and the bottom of the fissile zone did not change significantly. This is consistent with the axial power profile in Figure 6.

Figure 7 (right) shows axial distribution of U-235 atom density in a fuel assembly placed in zone batch #1 for the first six cycles. It was observed that U-235 depletion rate decreases with each cycle. Thus, it can be deduced that U-235 rapid depletion (after cycle #3) in the middle section of the fissile zone occurs when Pu-239 breeding gain is not enough to cover for the Pu-239 loss, which increases with decreasing U-235 atom density.

Figure 7 also shows a distinctive U-235 axial distribution feature for nodes #1 and #2. For a given depletion stage, U-235 atom density is increasing from node #1 to node #2 and is decreasing again for node #3. This was not observed in axial distributions of other actinides. This implicates that neutrons thermalize at the bottom of the active zone as well as at the top of the active zone.

Figure 7: Fuel assembly in Batch #1: Pu-239 (left) and U-235 (right) axial distribution for first 6 cycles

Figure 8 shows core reactivity as a function of time. Average relative error is 0.06%. Reactivity is decreasing from cycle #1 BOC to cycle #6 EOC (2100 days). It then reaches equilibrium at 3900 ± 52 pcm for BOC, 3400 ± 36 pcm for MOC, and 3000 ± 80 pcm for EOC. Similar reactivity trend was observed in the work of Krepel et al [8]. However, core reactivity, in this work, at cycle #1 BOC was by a factor of 2 higher, and equilibrium reactivity at BOC, MOC, and EOC was by a factor of 3 higher. The discrepancy in absolute reactivity values between this work and literature is mostly due to the missing radial neutron leakage and partly also due to the missing control rods, and corium discharge tubes.

Plot in Figure 8 indicates that fresh fuel insertion into the core induces higher reactivity increase for higher cycle numbers. This phenomenon is observed until equilibrium is reached after 6 cycles. This is due to fuel assemblies having similar reactivity worth through the first couple of cycles. As soon as burnup spatial distribution becomes more heterogeneous, insertion of fresh fuel assemblies has a greater impact on core reactivity.

Figure 8: Core reactivity

Figure 9 shows EOC axial power profile snapshots for the first 6 cycles. Power is normalized for 265 ± 5 W/cm. Introduction of fresh fuel has two distinctive effects on the overall axial power profile. Fresh fuel produces less power in the fertile region where the concentration of Pu-239 is lower in comparison to fertile region of a fuel assembly that has been inside the core for several cycles. Second effect fresh fuel has on the axial power profile is the increase of power production in the fissile region. Although

some U-238 is transmuted into Pu-239 in the fissile region, it cannot replace fast enough already fissioned Pu-239, U-235, and other minor actinides.

Figure 9: ESRF-SMART inner core batch-wise power distribution - EOC axial profiles

Cumulative axial burnup profiles of Batch #1 for 12 cycles and cycle-wise burnup profiles of Batch #1 for first 6 cycles are shown in Figure 10. The average burnup per cycle is 15.9 ± 0.4 MWday/kgHM. Total burnup of a fuel assembly is 99.8 ± 0.6 MWday/kgHM. Fertile region is subjected to soaring burnup rates as a fuel assembly is left longer in the core. This is due to transmutation of fertile U-238 into fissionable Pu-239. Contrary to the fertile region, the fissile region exhibits a relatively constant burnup rate. Burnup profile in the fissile region doesn't exhibit major discrepancies between the cycles. Only distinguishable discrepancies are located near the burnup peak of each burnup profile for a given cycle. Discrepancies between the peaks are a direct consequence of lower power magnitude at the peaks. Same features can be observed in the Figure 6, as burnup is directly correlated to fission power.

Figure 10: (left) one fuel assembly in Batch #1 is tracked over 6 cycles; the plot shows cycle-specific burnup profile (right) two fuel assemblies are tracked in Batch #1 over 12 cycles, first fuel assembly is tracked from cycle #1 to #6, and the second fuel assembly is tracked from cycle #7 to #12; the plot shows accumulated burnup profile

Figure 11: ESRF-SMART inner core accumulated burnup for fuel assemblies in each batch through the first 6 cycles - EOC axial profiles

Figure 11 shows evolution of axial burnup profiles for all six batches during the first six cycles. The most distinct feature that deviates from batch to batch is the burnup increase in the node #20. For some batches the increase is substantial, while for others it is not. This is due to batches' different power profiles. Slight profile deviations for fuel assemblies at the same depletion stages are inevitable due to stochastic nature of MC codes, especially when a low number of neutrons is simulated.

Summary and conclusion

A tool has been developed to calculate high fidelity axial burnup profiles of the ESFR-SMART inner core. Since there are no high-fidelity axial burnup results for the ESFR core in the literature, axial power profiles were used for the comparison. The absolute relative difference between this works' power profiles and literature is up to 10%. Since power and burnup have a linearly proportional relation, one can conclude that the same absolute relative difference can be found in burnup axial profiles as well.

With relatively small neutron statistics, relatively accurate axial burnup profiles can be achieved. A simulation of 12 full cycles (2100 days) can be achieved with 288 CPU hours. Comparison with the literature proved that BPP has potential for calculating the sodium void and Doppler coefficients. However, before commencing the simulations for safety relevant coefficients, the power of the base block needs to be adjusted. With the current power level of 42.86 MW for the base block, power tends to be higher in the fissile region, and lower in the fertile region when compared to literature results. In the next simulation run power needs to be set as reported by the deterministic codes for the inner region.

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